

Temporal variation in sugar exudation rate of hydroponically grown Pusa Basmati 1 at seedling stage

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Root exudates, along with dead root hairs, epidermal cells, and root caps, are a source of energy for the microbial community in the rhizoplane and rhizosphere. They aid in the mineralization of organic matter, nutrient cycling, and trace gas (CH_4 , N_2O , etc.) production (Aulakh et al 2001). MacRae and Castro (1966), Marathe (1970), and Waschutza et al (1992) have identified raffinose, glucose, fructose, arabinose, ribose, and xylose in rice exudates. Glucose is the most abundant of all sugar exudates of plants in general (Boureau 1977). With growth of rice, the exudation of organic acids such as oxalic, succinic, aconitic, citric, malic, tartaric, and lactic acids substitutes for the exudation of sugars (Aulakh et al 2001, Boureau 1977). Root and shoot biomass was positively correlated with carbon exudation, suggesting that it is driven by plant biomass (Aulakh et al 2001). A decrease in exudation was observed by Vancura et al (1977) when the source of seedling nutrition shifted from stored substances in the seeds and the endosperm to photosynthesizing leaves. As the nutrient supply from the leaves increases, root exudation increases again and maintains a rising trend up to the time of flowering.

Our study was undertaken to estimate the sugar exudation

rate of rice cultivar Pusa Basmati 1 during the seedling stage in a nutrient culture (Hoagland's solution). Pusa Basmati 1 is one of the most important rice varieties grown in India and in many other rice-growing Southeast Asian countries. The possibility of fitting the sugar exudation rate into mathematical functions was also explored.

Seeds of rice cultivar Pusa Basmati 1, obtained from the Division of Genetics of the Indian Agricultural Research Institute, were surface-sterilized by shaking with 70% ethanol for 2 min and then washing them thoroughly with sterile distilled water. Subsequently, the seeds were treated with 0.2% mercuric chloride solution for 30 min followed by repeated washing in sterile distilled water (MacRae and Castro 1996). The seeds were then allowed to germinate over moist filter paper in petri plates and allowed to grow for 96 h at 30 °C until the roots were conspicuous.

The seedlings were then transferred to cylindrical plastic containers (approx. 800 cm^3), containing

Hoagland's solution (1/4 strength as described by Johnson et al [1957]). Four seedlings were fixed in four small apertures at the top of each container. The containers were filled with Hoagland's solution up to the brim so that roots of the growing seedlings remained immersed in solution. The solution in the containers was aerated at regular intervals with the help of an aquarium pump to supply oxygen for root respiration (Fig. 1). Although root respiration of rice under anaerobic conditions takes place mainly via oxygen supply through the aerenchyma, in transplanted rice culture seedlings remain in the nursery for around 25 d initially, where the soil is not puddled and remains primarily aerobic. To simulate this condition in the seedbed, the nutrient solution was aerated at regular intervals.

Fig. 1. Cultivating rice seedlings in nutrient solution.

Sugar content in the nutrient medium was estimated 3, 6, 9, 12, 15, 18, 21, and 24 d after seedlings were transferred into Hoagland's solution. Different types of sugars were not estimated separately but total sugar was determined. Nutrient solution (1 mL) was withdrawn into a glass syringe (2 mL) through a side port fitted with a rubber septum (Fig. 1) and was mixed with 5 mL of concentrated sulfuric acid and 1 mL of phenol solution (5% in water, w/v) in a test tube. The tube was shaken vigorously and kept for about 20 min before absorbance of the solution was recorded at 490 nm in a spectrophotometer (Electronic Corporation of India Ltd., New Delhi). Total sugar was determined from a standard curve prepared from sucrose standards (Dubois et al 1956). Eight sets of containers, each replicated three times, were kept for sugar estimation and destructive plant sampling. After each sampling, one set of containers was taken, from which solution containing the released sugars was drawn. All four seedlings were then washed and dried in an oven at 60 °C for 24 h and weighed. To calculate the sugar exudation rate, cumulative sugar exudation during each 3-consecutive-day period was used.

A completely randomized design was followed to carry out analysis of variance (Gomez and Gomez 1984). Each represented datum is a mean $\pm$ SD of three replications. Duncan's multiple range test was used to calculate the statistically significant differences among each pair of means. All these statistical analyses were done by using MSTAT-C software (version 1.41), developed by the Crop and Soil Science Department of Michigan State University, USA. The sugar exudation

rate was curve-fitted by using MS Excel software (Microsoft Corporation, USA).

There was an increase in sugar exudation rate initially from 9.0 g kg⁻¹ dry biomass d⁻¹ on the 6th day. It declined from the 7th to the 9th day, and started increasing thereafter until 13.2 g kg⁻¹ dry biomass d⁻¹ was obtained on the 24th day (Fig. 2). The increase in root exudation rate during the first week was perhaps due to the nutrients derived from reserve substances in the seed endosperm. The transitional phase covering the transfer of nutrients from reserve substances to truly photosynthesizing leaves during the 2nd week is reflected in the low exudation rate of the sugars. When the true leaves had taken over from the 3rd week onward, exudation increased rapidly. The sugar exudation rate 24 d after root emergence had a significant correlation with plant biomass

Fig. 2. Changes in the amount of sugar released by hydroponically grown Pusa Basmati 1 seedlings. Bars indicate mean $\pm$ SD of three replications; values followed by the same letters are not statistically different from each other according to Duncan's multiple range test.

($r = 0.88$) and can be best fit by a 5th-order polynomial equation ($R^2 = 0.99$).

It will be interesting to study the sugar exudation rate of hydroponically grown Pusa Basmati 1 in the following stages and to determine whether this rate follows any particular distribution. Although exudation may differ

under field conditions, this study may help describe the sugar exudation behavior of Pusa Basmati 1 in nutrient cultures.

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